

Rice yield and evapotranspiration (ET) under different irrigation treatments. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Treatment	Yield (kg/2.7 m ²)		ET (mm) during different growth phases ^a				Water use efficiency (kg/ha-mm)
	Grain	Straw	Vegetative	Reproductive	Ripening	Total	
Continuous submergence	1.91	2.33	368 (54)	222 (33)	92 (13)	682	10.4
Water table at 30 cm	1.54	1.90	268 (56)	168 (35)	44 (9)	480	11.9
Water table at 60 cm	1.36	1.53	248 (70)	90 (25)	19 (5)	357	14.1
LSD (0.05)	0.29	0.45					

^aVegetative = 10 wk, reproductive = 6 wk, and ripening = 2 wk. Figures in parentheses are percent of total.

porosity) or change in submergence level and replenished accordingly. Rainfall contribution was accounted for. The total 1,990 mm rainfall received was well distributed over the growing season.

Continuous submergence gave significantly higher grain yield than water tables maintained at 30 cm and 60 cm depths (see table). But water use efficiency was highest with 60 cm water table and least with continuous submergence (see figure).

The rate of water used as ET was

highest in continuous submergence and depended a great deal on rainfall in any particular week. Water use was lowest with 60 cm water table and intermediate with 30 cm water table. The differences in ET became more pronounced later in the season.

The total water use as ET with continuous submergence was nearly double that with 60 cm water table. In all treatments, a major portion of total water was used during the vegetative

Weekly rainfall (mm)

Evapotranspiration behavior of rice under different water regimes. Uttar Pradesh, India.

phase; only one-fourth to one-third was used during the reproductive phase. With the 60 cm water table, more than two-thirds total ET was during the vegetative phase. □

Farming systems

Intercropping of pulses with rainfed rice at South Coastal Orissa, India

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We studied a feasible rice-based intercropping system to assure grain yield in at least one crop in case of erratic monsoon or other natural calamity. Under favorable climatic conditions, the additional income from an intercrop would augment earnings of small and marginal farmers.

Single crop rice (Parijat) was sown at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Green gram (K851), black gram (T9), peanut (AK12-24), red gram (Upas 120), and cowpea (C152) were sown as intercrops in rice: intercrop proportions of 1:1 (20 cm), 1:2

Grain yield of rice and intercrops. Berhampur, India.

Intercropping system	Yield (t/ha)			Return (\$/ha)		
	Main crop (rice)	Intercrop	Total	Main crop	Intercrop	Total
Rice + green gram	1.2	0.26	1.43	232	128	360
Rice + black gram	1.3	0.39	1.78	254	192	446
Rice + peanut	1.1	0.67	1.72	299	358	657
Rice + red gram	0.9	0.36	1.26	179	223	402
Rice + cowpea	1.1	0.40	1.51	221	214	435
Monocrop rice	2.2	**	2.23	444	**	444
Intercrop mixture						
1:1	1.7	0.50	2.22	**	**	**
1:2	1.0	0.59	1.63	**	**	**
2:1	0.9	0.32	1.25	**	**	**
2:2	0.7	0.41	1.13	**	**	**
LSD (0.05)	**	**	ns	**	**	**

(20,60 cm), 2:1 (20,60 cm), and 2:2 (20,60 cm), in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.60, 0.21% organic C, 18 kg available P/ha, and 227 kg exchangeable K/ha. Rice received 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha in 2 splits; pulses received 20-40-0 kg NPK/ha as basal.

Single crop rice produced 2.23 t/ha (see table). The rice yield was affected to different degrees by the intercrop. Highest rice yield was in rice + black gram at all proportions.

In the intercrops, peanut yielded the most (0.67 t/ha). The 1:2 intercrop resulted in higher intercrop yields (0.59 t/ha). □